

Brachyuran crabs in the selected coastal and freshwater areas in Basilan, Mindanao, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

Basilan is an island province in the southern part of the Philippines which is prominent for crab supply. The demand for marine products especially crabs in these areas are increasing and some inedible crabs are unintentionally caught by the fishermen and sold for medicinal purposes. This study was conceptualized to determine the marine and freshwater brachyuran crabs in urban areas of Basilan Province, Mindanao, Philippines particularly their identification and distribution as part of the crab resource management action plan. Using transect walk method, results revealed twenty-three (23) brachyuran crabs distributed in the urban areas of Basilan Province, Mindanao, Philippines. Of this, twelve (12) Families with 22 species are marine crabs, while only one (1) Family with one species (*Isolapotamon sinuatifrons*) comprises the freshwater crabs. Six of these are considered toxic crabs such as *Cardisoma carnifex*, *Geograpsus crinipes*, *Daldorfia horrida*, *Atergatis floridus*, *Etisus laevimanus* and *Zosimus aeneus*. Pearson Correlation results revealed that all physico-chemical parameters of the study site showed positive correlations and only pH, air temperature, Dissolved Oxygen (D.O.) and Total Suspended Solids (TSS) have significant correlations between the abundance of marine brachyuran crabs and the physico-chemical parameters of the study site. The incomplete identification of some species must be continued by incorporating molecular studies in order to identify new species, if possible.

Keywords: biodiversity, taxonomy, brachyurans, belt transect, Basilan Philippines

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INTRODUCTION

The diversity of brachyuran crabs includes 58 families, 207 genera and 522 species, as listed in the revised checklist of brachyuran crabs (Mendoza & Ng, 2008; Mendoza & Naruse, 2010; Mendoza & Ng, 2010). A study on the checklist of the crab species is of great importance for the formulation of conservation programs that will lead to the best understanding of community structure, ecological process and different problems faced by the ecosystem (Trivedi *et al.*, 2012).

Brachyuran crabs are found in both marine and freshwater aquatic ecosystems; but there are some that live in mud, only returns to water to release their larvae. Ecologically, these crabs are important as they play a significant role in the food chain. They are considered as one of the major decomposers through scavenging in the aquatic ecosystem (Kunsook & Dumrongrojwathana, 2017). Economically, humans utilize some of these crabs as a source of food. The chitin and chitosan extracted from crabs can be used for medicine and industrial applications and its meat is rich in vitamins and proteins and also carries therapeutic properties for colds, asthma and wheezing (Tharmine *et al.*, 2014).

Distribution of any marine organism is important to find out the different factors that affect them (Ravichandran *et al.*, 2010). According to Argañaraz & Gleiser (2017), as urbanization progresses, there are changes that affect arthropods' community over time in different habitats. The changes in the composition of the community can involve two phenomena: (a) spatial turnover which implies the replacement of some species with others, as a consequence of environmental sorting or spatial and historical constraints, and (b) species loss/gain which implies differences in species richness. Further, organic waste dump can cause environmental stress in coastal waters that affect the diversity of decapod crustaceans (Varadharajan *et al.*, 2013).

Basilan is an island province in the southernmost part of the Philippines. Two cities (Isabela and Lamitan City) are prominent for crab supply to its neighboring cities like Zamboanga City. Among the 45 barangays in each city, Barangay Baluno and Barangay Maloong San Jose are distinct for abundance of marine crabs and Barangay Tabiawan and Barangay Sengal are distinct for freshwater crabs.

The demand for marine products especially crabs in these areas is increasing. Some crabs that are not edible are also unintentionally caught by the fishermen and sold for medicinal purposes in order to gain more income to sustain their everyday needs. The marine and freshwater crabs in Basilan need to be documented for conservation purposes. Hence, this study was conceptualized to determine the distribution of marine and freshwater brachyuran crabs in urban areas of Basilan Province, Mindanao, Philippines and to evaluate the different physico-chemical parameters affecting its distribution.

METHODS

The study was conducted in the two cities of Basilan Province: namely, Isabela City and Lamitan City, Basilan. Isabela City is 27.4 km away from Lamitan City Proper. Figures 1 and 2 show the satellite base map and the actual study site of each marine sampling area while Figures 3 and 4 show the freshwater sites.

Figure 1. Satellite Base Map of Kalabasa Beach (left) and Actual Site (right).

Figure 2. Satellite Base Map of Malo-ong Canal (left) and Actual Site (right).

Figure 3. Tabiawan River, Lamitan City, Basilan.

Figure 4. Sengal River, Lamitan City, Basilan.

For the marine study sites (Fig. 1 & 2), three belt transects each measuring 500m² with 2,150-m interval between them were established in each study sites. The researchers used transect walk and hand picking technique inside the established belt transects. On the other hand, freshwater crabs were collected in the sampling areas of Tabiawan River (Fig. 3) and Sengal River (Fig. 4) each having three stations. Crabs within the left side per station were collected using hand picking, fish netting and rock and roll methods.

Sample collections were conducted in the months of April, June and August 2018, specifically during low tide for marine ecosystems. Samples collected were submerged in 85% ethyl alcohol and properly placed and labeled in a plastic container. Each sample was photographed upon collection and documented using a 550D DSLR Camera showing dorsal and ventral view of the crabs. Identification of crab species was based on their morphological features such as the size of the carapace, color and number of legs present and also corroborated with literature, books and published articles. The identified species were also verified by experts who are carcinologists, specifically researchers on crabs.

Determination of physico-chemical parameters known to influence the distribution of brachyuran crabs was also conducted. This includes the following parameters:

1. pH

The pH of water samples from each site was measured through immersing the pH meter three different times.

2. Water Temperature

The value of the water temperature was recorded immediately after collection to avoid error during the sampling process by using a thermometer immersed in water for 5min, with three trials at 10min intervals.

3. Air Temperature

Air temperature readings were obtained immediately after collection and were recorded for 5min, with three trials at 10min intervals.

4. Salinity

Water salinity was recorded immediately in the different areas of sampling stations using a refractometer. Three drops of water sample in every station were dropped into the refractometer and took three seconds for the results.

5. Dissolve Oxygen (DO)

Water samples were brought to the Department of Science and Technology (DOST) IX using the standard procedure:

Two (2) ml of MnSO₄ and 2ml of alkaline iodide-azide were added into the BOD bottle containing the water sample. The bottle was instantly covered to prevent air bubbles to be trapped and inverted several times. An orange brown precipitate formed and allowed to settle for a few minutes. Two (2) ml of conc. H₂SO₄ was added in the solution and the bottle inverted again several times until the precipitate dissolved producing an orange-colored solution. The prepared sample was lessened by transferring about 97ml of its content into 250ml graduated cylinder. The sample was titrated with 0.25 M Na₂S₂O₃ solution to pale yellow color. Two (2) ml of starch indicator was added into the solution and continued the titration until a color transition from blue to colorless was observed. The dispensed volume of 0.025 M Na₂S₂O₃ was used to calculate the dissolved oxygen in the sample using this formula:

$$D.O. (ppm) = \frac{(\text{Actual D.O}) \times (V) \times (1000)}{1000 \text{ ml sample}}$$

6. Total Suspended Solids

Water samples were brought to the Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources (BFAR) using the standard procedure. One thousand (1000) ml water samples were collected from the three stations of each study site and filtered using Whatman paper. The filter paper was pre-weighed and oven dried. The residue in the filter paper was rinsed with hot water and dried in an oven. Suspended solids were calculated in terms of mg/l using the formula:

$$\text{TSS} = \frac{\text{Increase in weight}}{\text{volume of sample}} \times 10^6$$

Ecological analyses are also important in assessing the organisms' distribution. These include the following:

1. Abundance

$$\text{Abundance} = \text{Total number of individual species per site}$$

2. Species Richness

This was determined by counting the number of different species found in study site.

Statistical analysis includes the use of Pearson correlation which evaluates the correlation between the abundance of crabs' species and the physico-chemical parameters determined in each study site.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A total of twenty-three (23) brachyuran crabs are distributed in the urban areas of Basilan Province, Mindanao, Philippines. Of this, twelve (12) Families with 22 species are marine crabs while only one (1) Family with one species (*Isolapotamon sinuatifrons*) comprises the freshwater crabs. Six of these are considered toxic crabs such as *Cardisoma carnifex*, *Geograpsus crinipes*, *Daldorfia horrida*, *Atergatis floridus*, *Etisus laevimanus* and *Zosimus aeneus*. (Table 1; Figures 5-27).

Table 1. Families of marine and freshwater brachyuran crabs found in the study sites.

Marine Crabs	
Family	Species
Callapidae	<i>Calappa capellonis</i>
Gecarcinidae	<i>Cardisoma carnifex</i> *
	<i>Epigrapsus</i> sp.
Grapsidae	<i>Geograpsus crinipes</i> *
	<i>Micippa philyra</i>
Majidae	<i>Camposcia retusa</i>
Macrophthalmidae	<i>Macrophthalmus</i> sp.
Matutidae	<i>Ashtoret lunaris</i>
Ocypodidae	<i>Ocypode ceratophthalmus</i>
Parthenopidae	<i>Daldorfia horrida</i> *
Pilumnidae	<i>Pilumnus</i> sp. 1
	<i>Pilumnus sluiteri</i>
Portunidae	<i>Portunus convexus</i>
	<i>Portunus pelagicus</i>
	<i>Thalamita</i> sp. 1
	<i>Thalamita</i> sp. 2
	<i>Thalamita</i> sp. 3
	<i>Thalamita spinimana</i>
Varunidae	<i>Varuna litterata</i>
Xanthidae	<i>Atergatis floridus</i> *
	<i>Etisus laevimanus</i> *
	<i>Zosimus aeneus</i> *
Freshwater Crabs	
Potamidae	<i>Isolapotamon sinuatifrons</i>

* Indicates non-edible crab

Figure 5. *Calappa capellonis* (Laurie, 1906): **A**-dorsal view; **B**-ventral view.

Figure 6. *Cardisoma carnifex* (Herbst, 1796): **A**-dorsal view; **B**-ventral view.

Figure 7. *Epigrapsus* sp.: **A**-dorsal view; **B**-ventral view.

Figure 8. *Geograpsus crinipes* (Dana, 1851): **A**-dorsal view; **B**-ventral view.

Figure 9. *Micippa philyra* (Herbst, 1803): **A**-dorsal view; **B**-ventral view.

Figure 10. *Camposcia retusa*: **A**-dorsal view; **B**-ventral view.

Figure 11. *Macrophthalmus* sp.: **A**-dorsal view; **B**-ventral view.

Figure 12. *Ashtoret lunaris* (Forskål, 1775): **A**-dorsal view; **B**-ventral view.

Figure 13. *Ocypode ceratophthalmus* (Pallas, 1772): **A**-dorsal view; **B**-ventral view.

Figure 14. *Daldorfia horrida* (Linnaeus, 1758): **A**-dorsal view; **B**-ventral view.

Figure 15. *Pilumnus* sp. 1: **A**-dorsal view; **B**-ventral view.

Figure 16. *Pilumnus sluiteri* (de Man, 1892): **A**-dorsal view; **B**-ventral view

Figure 17. *Portunus convexus* (De Haan, 1835): **A**-dorsal view; **B**-ventral view.

Figure 18. *Portunus pelagicus* (Linnaeus, 1758): **A**-dorsal view; **B**-ventral view.

Figure 19. *Thalamita* sp. 1: **A**-dorsal view; **B**-ventral view.

Figure 20. *Thalamita* sp. 2: **A**-dorsal view; **B**-ventral view.

Figure 21. *Thalamita* sp. 3: **A**-dorsal view; **B**-ventral view

Figure 22. *Thalamita spinimana* (Dana, 1852): **A**-dorsal view; **B**-ventral view.

Figure 23. *Varuna litterata* (Fabricius, 1798): **A**-dorsal view; **B**-ventral view.

Figure 24. *Atergatis floridus* (Linnaeus, 1767): **A**-dorsal view; **B**-ventral view.

Figure 25. *Etisus laevimanus* (Randall, 1840): **A**-dorsal view; **B**-ventral view.

Figure 26. *Zosimus aeneus* (Linnaeus, 1758): **A**-dorsal view; **B**-ventral view.

Figure 27. *Isolapotamon sinuatifrons*: **A**- dorsal view; **B**- ventral view.

Figures 28 and 29 show the abundance of each brachyuran crabs found in the study sites during the sampling periods.

Figure 28. Abundance of Marine crabs species found in Kalabasa Beach, Isabela City and Malo-ong Canal, Lamitan City in the months of April, June and August 2018.

Figure 29. Abundance of freshwater crab (*I. sinuatifrons*) found in Tabiawan River, Isabela City and Sengal River, Lamitan City for three months (April, June and August).

Thalamita spinimana shows the highest abundance in Kalabasa Beach, Isabela City with a total of 32 individuals and *Thalamita* sp. 3, *Ocypode ceratophthalmus*, *Geograpsus crinipes*, *Epigrapsus* sp., *Daldorfia horrida*, *Cardisoma carnifex* and *Calappa capellonis* exhibit the lowest abundance in the said area. On the other hand, in Malo-ong Canal, Lamitan City, *Portunus* sp. 1 shows the highest abundance of marine crabs species with a total of 29 individuals while the least abundant species are *Varuna litterata*, *Thalamita* sp. 2, *Ocypode ceratophthalmus*, *Macrophthalmus* sp., *Geograpsus crinipes*, *Epigrapsus* sp., *Daldorfia horrida*, and *Cardisoma carnifex*. For the freshwater ecosystem, only 1 species was found, the *Isolapotamon sinuatifrons* (Fig. 28). Table 2 shows the species richness of the brachyuran marine crabs in Basilan Province.

Table 2. Species richness of marine and freshwater crabs in Basilan Province.

Species Richness	Marine	
	Kalabasa Beach, Isabela City	Malo-ong Canal, Lamitan City
	19	22
Species Richness	Freshwater	
	Tabiawan River, Isabela City	Sengal River, Lamitan City
	1	1

Highest species richness was exhibited in Maloong Canal, Lamitan City for the marine brachyuran crabs; however, even in the freshwater area it exhibited the least with only one (1) species. Table 3 shows the obtained physicochemical parameters in each selected sampling sites in Basilan Province.

Table 3. Physicochemical parameters in each selected sampling sites in Basilan Province.

Parameters	Month	Location			
		Marine		Freshwater	
		Kalabasa Beach, Isabela City	Malo-ong Canal, Lamitan	Tabiawan River, Isabela City	Sengal River, Isabela City
pH	April	7.2	7.2	6.6	6.5
	June	7.0	7.0	6.5	6.3
	August	6.8	7.2	6.6	6.5
Water Temperature (°C)	April	29	27	28	28
	June	27	26.5	27	26
	August	27	28	28	28
Air Temperature (°C)	April	29	27	28	27
	June	27	27	27	27
	August	27.5	28	28	28
Salinity (ppt)	April	30	32	-	-
	June	29.5	30	-	-
	August	29	32	-	-
DO (mg/l)	April	7.35	9.10	5.42	3.68
	June	7.11	8.98	4.98	3.05
	August	7.01	9.02	5.13	3.98
TSS (mg/l)	April	3084	3372	236	224
	June	2940	3255	188	156
	August	3012	3192	198	202

The physico-chemical parameters obtained are still within acceptable range compared to other studies focusing on effects of physico-chemical parameters on crab biodiversity. Unsuitable physico-chemical parameters affect the distribution of crabs (Bandra *et al.*, 2013; Varadharajan *et al.*, 2013).

Table 4 shows the result of the presence and absence of the different brachyuran crabs in the different study sites during the sampling period April, June and August, 2018.

Table 4. Presence and absence of the different brachyuran crabs in the different study sites during the sampling period April, June and August, 2018.

Species	Marine					
	Kalabasa, Beach Isabela City			Malo-ong Canal, Lamitan City		
	April	June	August	April	June	August
<i>Ashtoret lunaris</i>	-	-	-	+	+	-
<i>Atergatis floridus</i>	+	-	+	+	-	+
<i>Calappa capellonis</i>	+	-	-	-	-	+
<i>Camposcia retusa</i>	+	+	+	-	-	+
<i>Cardisoma carnifex</i>	+	-	-	-	-	+
<i>Daldorfia horrida</i>	+	-	-	-	-	+
<i>Epigrapsus</i> sp.	-	+	-	-	-	+
<i>Etisus laevimanus</i>	+	-	-	-	-	+
<i>Geograpsus crinipes</i>	+	-	-	-	-	+
<i>Macrothalmus</i> sp.	-	-	-	-	-	+
<i>Micippa philyra</i>	+	-	-	+	-	+
<i>Ocypode ceratophthalmus</i>	-	-	+	-	-	+
<i>Pilumnus sluiteri</i>	+	+	-	-	-	+
<i>Portunus</i> sp. 1	+	+	-	+	-	-
<i>Portunus convexus</i>	+	+	+	+	-	+
<i>Portunus pelagicus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Thalamita</i> sp. 1	+	-	-	+	-	-
<i>Thalamita</i> sp. 2	+	-	-	-	+	-
<i>Thalamita</i> sp.3	+	-	-	-	+	-
<i>Thalamita spinimana</i>	+	-	+	+	+	-
<i>Varuna litterata</i>	-	-	-	-	-	+
<i>Zosimus aeneus</i>	+	+	-	+	-	-
<i>Isolapotamon sinuatifrons</i>	Freshwater					
	Tabiawan River, Isabela City			Sengal River, Lamitan City		
	April	June	August	April	June	August
	+	+	+	+	+	+

+ Indicates presence in the Area on the sampling schedule

- Indicates absence in the Area on the sampling schedule

Tables 5-8 show the correlation between abundance of brachyuran crabs in each sampling site and the respective physico-chemical parameters.

Table 5. Correlations between abundance of marine brachyuran crabs in Kalabasa Beach, Isabela City and the physico-chemical parameters.

Physico-chemical Parameters	<i>r</i> value	Permutation <i>p</i>
pH	1	0.0512
Water temperature	1	0.0814
Air temperature	1	0.0026*
Salinity	1	0.2593
Dissolved Oxygen (DO)	1	0.0449*
Total Suspended Solids (TSS)	1	0.0153*

* Significant at $\alpha < 0.05$ **Table 6.** Correlations between abundance of marine brachyuran crabs in Malo-ong Canal, Lamitan City and the physico-chemical parameters.

Physico-chemical Parameters	<i>r</i> value	Permutation <i>p</i>
pH	1	0.0000*
Water temperature	1	0.9121
Air temperature	1	0.3869
Salinity	1	0.9275
Dissolved Oxygen (DO)	1	0.9318
Total Suspended Solids (TSS)	1	0.7999

* Significant at $\alpha < 0.05$ **Table 7.** Correlations between abundance of the freshwater *I. sinuatifrons* in Tabiawan River, Isabela City and physico-chemical parameters.

Physico-chemical Parameters	<i>r</i> value	Permutation <i>p</i>
pH	1	0.0000*
Water temperature	1	0.6453
Air temperature	1	0.6453
Dissolved Oxygen (DO)	1	0.0000*
Total Suspended Solids (TSS)	1	0.0000*

*Significant at $\alpha < 0.05$

Table 8. Correlations between abundance of the freshwater *Isolapotamon sinuatifrons* in Sengal River, Lamitan City and physico-chemical parameters.

Physico-chemical Parameters	<i>r</i> value	Permutation <i>p</i>
pH	1	0.88869
Water temperature	0.30738	0.62588
Air temperature	1	0.97771
Dissolved Oxygen (DO)	1	0.94543
Total Suspended Solids (TSS)	1	0.93748

* Significant at $\alpha < 0.05$

The environmental parameters of the said areas are very important because the variations in the physico-chemical parameters like pH, temperature, salinity, DO and TSS can affect the abundance and distribution of crustaceans. According to Bandral *et al.* (2013), pH influences the metabolism, physiology and maturation process in decapods.

Temperature is also a limiting factor in aquatic environment and considerably affects various metabolic activities, growth, oxygen consumption, reproduction, molting, survival, distribution and migratory behavior of crustaceans (Bandral *et al.*, 2013). According to Varadharajan *et al.* (2013), salinity is an ecological master factor in the distribution of living organisms, which is likely to influence decapod crab's distribution and the production in coastal ecosystems.

Salinity observed for both the marine sites ranged from 29-32 ppt. The salinity was high during April and August in Malo-ong Canal since April is considered summer and there was no rain in the month of August during the sampling period. As for the lowest value of salinity, it was recorded in Kalabasa Beach during the month of June and August since these months were recorded as monsoon or rainy season in Basilan. For the freshwater ecosystem, salinity was not recorded since the concentration of salt was nearly zero.

Dissolved oxygen (DO) concentrations clearly influence the behavior of decapods and life strategies in terms of oxygen consumption and energy content; the decreased DO is due to the increase of temperature and salinity (Varadharajan *et al.*, 2013). DO can enter water as a by-product of photosynthesis and takes place in the surface of the water by algae and other plants but most of the process takes place underwater by seaweeds, sub-surface algae and others.

Total suspended solids (TSS) include a wide variety of material, such as decaying plants and animal matter, industrial wastes and sewage. TSS levels can influence aquatic life from phytoplankton to crustaceans, especially when the individual particles are small carrying substances that are harmful or toxic. In coastal zones, however, these fine particles are food source for filter feeders which are part of the food chain leading to bio-magnifications of chemical pollutants in crustaceans and ultimately in man, since intertidal area deposition of fine particles effectively removes pollutants from the overlying water by burying them in the bottom sediments of the coastal zones (Varadharajan *et al.*, 2013). The values recorded for TSS in marine water was between 2940-3372mg/l for the lowest value; while for the freshwater, the TSS ranged from 156-236mg/l.

Pearson Correlation results revealed that all physico-chemical parameters of the study site showed positive correlations and only air temperature, Total Suspended Solids and

Dissolved Oxygen have significant correlation for Kalabasa Beach and pH revealed highly significant correlation for Malo-ong.

For the collection of freshwater crabs in both study sites, it showed positive correlation but no significant correlation between the *Isolapotamon sinuatifrons* and the physico-chemical parameters of the said sites.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study recorded a total of 12 Families with 22 species of marine brachyuran crabs and only one species of freshwater crabs under Family Potamidae was recorded. Marine crabs are more abundant than the freshwater crabs. More crabs were found in the month of April in Kalabasa Beach with a total of 110 species and in the month of August in Sengal River with a total of 645 species. Family Portunidae showed the most abundant family of crabs with 6 species: *Portunus convexus*, *Portunus pelagicus*, *Thalamita* sp.1, *Thalamita* sp. 2, *Thalamita* sp. 3 and *Thalamita spinimana*. *Portunus* sp.1 shows the highest abundance among the 22 marine crab species. Results also showed *Varuna litterata* and *Macrophthalmus* sp. are the least abundant species. *Ashtoret lunaris*, *Macrophthalmus* sp. and *Varuna litterata* were not observed in Kalabasa Beach making Malo-ong Canal beach richer in species than Kalabasa Beach. The *Isolapotamon sinuatifrons* under Family Potamidae is the only freshwater crab found. Pearson's Correlation showed that the four study sites showed positive correlation, but only Kalabasa beach showed significant correlation of air temperature, Dissolved Oxygen and Total Suspended Solids between the abundance of brachyuran crabs collected and the physico-chemical parameters of the said site. More sampling time can be done to get the species accumulation curve between rainy and dry seasons. More areas are to be researched regarding crabs to get more data either on new species or possible new species.

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